

A guide to selecting high-performing antibodies for Beclin-1 (Q14457) for use in western blot, immunoprecipitation and flow cytometry

Congyao Zha¹, Michael S. Biddle^{†2}, Charles Alende^{†1}, Maryam Fotouhi^{†1}, Carolyn Jones², Sara González Bolívar¹, Riham Ayoubi¹, Vincent Francis¹, Peter S. McPherson¹, Carl Laflamme^{1*} and Harvinder Virk^{2*}, NeuroSGC/YCharOS/EDDU collaborative group and ABIF consortium

[†] Authors contributed equally

¹ Department of Neurology and Neurosurgery, Structural Genomics Consortium, The Montreal Neurological Institute, McGill University, Montreal, Quebec, Canada

² NIHR BRC-Respiratory, University of Leicester, Leicester, England, UK

* Corresponding authors: carl.laflamme@mcgill.ca, hsv6@leicester.ac.uk

Abstract

Beclin-1 is a regulator of membrane trafficking with key roles in autophagy. Here we have characterized nineteen Beclin-1 commercial antibodies for western blot and immunoprecipitation, and sixteen antibodies for flow cytometry using a standardized experimental protocol based on comparing read-outs in knockout cell lines and isogenic parental controls. These studies are part of a larger, collaborative initiative seeking to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercially available antibodies for human proteins and publishing the results openly as a resource for the scientific community. While the use of antibodies and protocols vary between laboratories, we encourage readers to use this report as a guide to select the most appropriate antibodies for their specific needs.

Keywords:

UniProt ID Q14457, *BECN1*, Beclin-1, antibody characterization, antibody validation, western blot, immunoprecipitation, immunofluorescence, flow cytometry

Introduction

Beclin-1 is a 450-amino acid protein with a central role in autophagy regulation; it forms a complex with the Class III Phosphoinositide 3-Kinase (PI3K) to initiate autophagy. Beclin-1 contains an N-terminal BCL-2 homology-3 (BH3) domain and a coiled-coil domain for protein-protein interactions, in addition to a C terminal Evolutionarily Conserved Domain (ECD) essential for membrane binding (1). This protein ameliorates Parkinson's disease pathogenesis by enhancing autophagy and degradation of α -synuclein (2, 3).

This research is part of a broader collaborative initiative in which academics, funders and commercial antibody manufacturers are working together to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercial antibodies for human proteins using standardized protocols, and openly sharing the data (4). It consists of identifying human cell lines with adequate target protein expression and the development/contribution of equivalent knockout (KO) cell lines, followed by antibody characterization procedures using most commercially available renewable antibodies against the corresponding protein (4). Here we characterized nineteen commercial Beclin-1 antibodies in western blot and immunoprecipitation, and sixteen commercial antibodies in flow cytometry. Antibodies were selected and donated by participant antibody manufacturers, for use in western blot, immunoprecipitation, and flow cytometry enabling biochemical and cellular assessment of Beclin-1 properties and function.

The authors do not engage in result analysis or offer explicit antibody recommendations. Our primary aim is to deliver top-tier data to the scientific community, grounded in Open Science principles. This empowers experts to interpret the characterization data independently, enabling them to make informed choices regarding the most suitable antibodies for their specific experimental needs. Guidelines on how to interpret antibody characterization data found in this study are featured on the YCharOS gateway (5) and in Table 5 of this data note (4).

Results and discussion

Our standard protocol involves comparing readouts from wild type (WT) and KO cells (6, 7). The first step was to identify a cell line(s) that expresses sufficient levels of a given protein to generate a measurable signal using antibodies. To this end, we examined the DepMap (Cancer Dependency Map Portal, RRID:SCR_017655) transcriptomics database to identify all cell lines that express the target at levels greater than $2.5 \log_2$ (transcripts per million "TPM" + 1), which we have found to be a suitable cut-off (8). The HeLa expresses the *BECN1* transcript at $5.7 \log_2$ TPM+1, and a *BECN1* KO HeLa cell line was obtained from Abcam (Table 1) to conduct antibody screening. Moreover, as seen on DepMap, the HeLa does not carry mutations in the *BECN1* that could affect antibody-epitope binding.

To screen the nineteen antibodies (Table 2) by western blot, WT and *BECN1* KO protein lysates were ran on SDS-PAGE, transferred onto nitrocellulose membranes, and then probed with all nineteen Beclin-1 antibodies in parallel (Figure 1). Additionally, the differential expression of Beclin-1 was evaluated by western blot across multiple cancer cell lines (Figure 2).

We then assessed the capability of all nineteen antibodies to capture Beclin-1 from HeLa protein extracts using immunoprecipitation techniques, followed by western blot analysis. For the immunoblot step, a specific Beclin-1 antibody identified previously (refer to Figure 1) was selected. Equal amounts of the starting material (SM) and the unbound fractions (UB), as well as the whole immunoprecipitate (IP) eluates were separated by SDS-PAGE (Figure 3).

For flow cytometry, HeLa WT and *BECN1* KO cells were labelled with distinct fluorescent dyes and combined at a 1:1 ratio. Both cell lines were fixed, permeabilized and blocked in the same tube prior to antibody staining to reduce bias. Sixteen Beclin-1 antibodies (Table 3) were then evaluated, with fluorescent intensity assessed using the Attune NxT flow cytometer. Antibody staining in both WT and KO line was then quantified using FlowJo software, with representative histograms presented in Figure 4.

In conclusion, we have screened nineteen Beclin-1 commercial antibodies by western blot and immunoprecipitation and sixteen commercial antibodies by flow cytometry by comparing the signal produced by the antibodies in human HeLa WT and *BECN1* KO cells. To assist users in interpreting antibody performance, Table 5 outlines various scenarios in which antibodies may perform in the three applications (8). High-quality and renewable antibodies that successfully detect Beclin-1 were identified in all applications. Researchers who wish to study Beclin-1 in a different species are encouraged to select high-quality antibodies, based on the results of this study, and investigate the predicted species reactivity of the manufacturer before extending their research.

Limitations

Inherent limitations are associated with the antibody characterization platform used in this study. Firstly, the YCharOS project focuses on renewable (recombinant and monoclonal) antibodies and does not test all commercially available Beclin-1 antibodies. YCharOS partners provide approximately 80% of all renewable antibodies, but some top-cited polyclonal antibodies may not be available through these partners. We encourage readers to consult vendor documentation to identify the specific antigen each antibody is raised against, where such information is available.

Secondly, the YCharOS effort employs a non-biased approach that is agnostic to the protein for which antibodies have been characterized. The aim is to provide objective data on antibody performance without preconceived notions about how antibodies should perform or the molecular weight that should be observed in western blot. As the authors are not experts in Beclin-1, only a brief overview of the protein's function and its relevance in disease is provided. Beclin-1 experts are invited to analyze and interpret observed banding patterns in western blots and subcellular localization in immunofluorescence.

Thirdly, YCharOS experiments are not performed in replicates primarily due to the use of multiple antibodies targeting various epitopes. Once a specific antibody is identified, it validates the protein expression of the intended target in the selected cell line, confirms the lack of protein expression in the KO cell line and supports conclusions regarding the specificity of the other antibodies. All experiments are performed using master mixes, and meticulous attention is paid to sample preparation and experimental execution. In IF, the use of two different concentrations serves to evaluate antibody specificity and can aid in assessing assay reliability. In instances where antibodies yield no signal, a repeat experiment is conducted following titration. Additionally, our independent data is performed subsequently to the antibody manufacturers internal validation process, therefore making our characterization process a repeat.

Lastly, as comprehensive and standardized procedures are respected, any conclusions remain confined to the experimental conditions and cell line used for this study. The use of a single cell type for evaluating antibody performance poses as a limitation, as factors such as target protein abundance significantly impact results. Additionally, the use of cancer cell lines containing gene mutations poses a potential challenge, as these mutations may be within the epitope coding sequence or other regions of the gene responsible for the intended target. Such alterations can impact the binding affinity of antibodies. This represents an inherent limitation of any approach that employs cancer cell lines.

Method

The standardized protocols used to carry out this KO cell line-based antibody characterization platform was established and approved by a collaborative group of academics, industry researchers and antibody manufacturers. The detailed materials and step-by-step protocols used to characterize antibodies in western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence are openly available on Protocols.io ([protocols.io/view/a-consensus-platform-for-antibody-characterization](https://www.protocols.io/view/a-consensus-platform-for-antibody-characterization)) (4). Brief descriptions of the experimental setup used to carry out this study can be found below.

Cell lines and antibodies

The cell lines used in this study are listed in Table 1. Primary antibodies used in western blot and immunoprecipitation, and those used in flow cytometry are listed in Table 2 and 3, respectively. Secondary antibodies are listed in Table 4. To ensure consistency with manufacturer recommendations and account for proprietary formulations (where antibody concentrations are not disclosed), antibody usage is reported as dilution ratios rather than absolute concentrations. To facilitate proper citation and unambiguous identification, all cell lines and antibodies are referenced with their corresponding Research Resource Identifiers (RRIDs), when available (9, 10). All cell lines used in this study were regularly tested for mycoplasma contamination and were confirmed to be mycoplasma-free.

Antibody screening by western blot

HeLa WT and *BECN1* KO cells were collected in RIPA buffer (25mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 150mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 89901) supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number P8340). Lysates were sonicated briefly and incubated 30 min on ice. Lysates were spun at $\sim 110,000 \times g$ for 15 min at 4°C and equal protein aliquots of the supernatants were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and western blot. BLUelf prestained protein ladder (GeneDireX, cat. number PM008-0500) was used.

Western blots were performed with precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number WXP42012BOX) ran with Tris/Glycine/SDS buffer (Bio-Rad, cat. number 1610772), loaded in Laemmli loading sample buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number AAJ61337AD) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau S staining (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP103-10) which is scanned to show together with individual western blot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) (Cell Signalling Technology, cat. number 9997). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated at a dilution of $\sim 0.2 \mu\text{g/ml}$ in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes were incubated with Pierce ECL (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 32106) prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number A44240).

Antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Antibody-bead conjugates were prepared by adding 2 µg to 500 µl of Pierce IP Lysis Buffer from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 87788) in a microcentrifuge tube, together with 30 µl of Dynabeads protein A- (for rabbit antibodies) or protein G- (for mouse antibodies) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 10002D and 10004D, respectively). Anti-Beclin-1 MA5-15825* was at an unknown concentration and thus 5 µl were tested in IP. All tubes were rocked for ~1 h at 4°C followed by two washes to remove unbound antibodies.

HeLa WT were collected in Pierce IP buffer (25 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1% NP-40 and 5% glycerol) supplemented with protease inhibitor. Lysates were rocked 30 min at 4°C and spun at 110,000 x g for 15 min at 4°C. 0.5 ml aliquots at 1 mg/ml of lysate were incubated with an antibody-bead conjugate for ~1 h at 4°C. The unbound fractions were collected, and beads were subsequently washed three times with 1.0 ml of IP buffer and processed for SDS-PAGE and western blot on precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels.

Antibody screening by flow cytometry

HeLa WT and *BECN1* KO cells were detached, and four million cells were labelled with CellTracker green or violet fluorescent dyes, respectively (Thermo Fisher Scientific, #C7025 and #C10094). WT and KO cells were then centrifuged at 300 x g for 10 minutes and resuspended in PBS containing 1% bovine serum albumin (BSA) (Sigma-Aldrich, A9647). Cell populations were then combined at a 1:1 ratio, centrifuged and fixed on ice for 20 minutes using 800 µL of 4% PFA in PBS (Thermo Fisher Scientific #J19943.K2). Following fixation, 1.2 mL of 1% BSA in PBS was added to the tube, vortexed and centrifuged at 600 x g for 15 minutes at 4°C. Cells were then permeabilised in 400 µL PBS with 0.1% Triton X-100 (Thermo Fisher Scientific #J63521) for 10 minutes at room temperature, centrifuged at 600 x g for 15 minutes at 4°C and then blocked with 5% goat serum (Sigma-Aldrich #G6767), 1% BSA in PBS for 30 minutes on ice. After the blocking step 400,000 cells were aliquoted into individually labelled tubes, centrifuged at 600 x g for 15 minutes at 4°C and incubated in 150µL of 1% BSA PBS with Beclin-1 primary antibodies for 30 minutes on ice. 500µL of 1% BSA PBS was then added to each tube, vortexed and centrifuged at 600 x g for 15 minutes at 4°C. Cells were then incubated with their corresponding Multi-rAb CoraLite® Plus 647 secondary antibodies (0.83 µg/ml) in 150 µl of 1% BSA PBS for 30 minutes on ice. 500 µl of 1% BSA PBS was then added to each tube, vortexed and centrifuged 600 x g for 15 minutes at 4°C.

Tubes were then resuspended in 1 ml of 1% BSA in PBS and data was acquired using the Attune NxT flow cytometer. Data was analysed using FlowJo with the following gates. The cell population was first gated on FSC-A vs SSC-A, within that gate single cells were selected by FSC-A vs FSC-H and then KO and WT cells were isolated by BL1-A vs VL1-A using a quadrat gate. Quantification of antibody staining was then observed in the RL1-A channel and histograms merged to demonstrate the staining intensity between the two populations compared to the two secondary only controls. The figure was then assembled using Adobe Illustrator 2024.

Data availability*Underlying data*

Zenodo: Dataset for the Beclin-1 antibody screening study <to be submitted>

Data are available under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license (CC-BY 4.0).

Grant information

This work was supported by the Michael J. Fox Foundation for Parkinson's Research (MJFF) (grant no. 18331). This work was also supported by a grant from the Quebec Consortium for Drug Discovery (CQDM), a grant from the Ministère de l'Économie, de l'Innovation et de l'Énergie du Québec.

The funders had no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript.

Competing interests

For this project, the authors developed partnerships with leading antibody manufacturers and KO cell line providers. The partners provide antibodies and KO cell lines to this project at no cost. These partners include: Abcam, ABCD antibodies, ABclonal, Addgene, Aviva Systems Biology, BioTechne, Cell Signaling Technology, Developmental Studies Hybridoma Bank, GeneTex, Horizon Discovery, Institute for Protein Innovation, MilliporeSigma, Proteintech, Synaptic Systems, Thermo Fisher Scientific.

Acknowledgment

We would like to thank the NeuroSGC/YCharOS/EDDU collaborative group for their important contribution to the creation of an open scientific ecosystem of antibody manufacturers and KO cell line suppliers, for the development of community-agreed protocols, and for their shared ideas, resources, and collaboration. Members of the group can be found below. We would also like to thank the Advanced BioImaging Facility (ABIF) consortium for their image analysis pipeline development and conduction (RRID:SCR_017697). Members of each group can be found below.

NeuroSGC/YCharOS/EDDU collaborative group: Thomas M. Durcan, Aled M. Edwards, Peter S. McPherson, Chetan Raina and Wolfgang Reintsch

ABIF consortium: Claire M. Brown and Joel Ryan

Thank you to the Structural Genomics Consortium, a registered charity (no. 1097737), for your support on this project. The Structural Genomics Consortium receives funding from Bayer AG, Boehringer Ingelheim, Bristol-Myers Squibb, Genentech, Genome Canada through Ontario Genomics Institute (grant no. OGI-196), the EU and EFPIA through the Innovative Medicines Initiative 2 Joint Undertaking (EUbOPEN grant no. 875510), Janssen, Merck KGaA (also known as EMD in Canada and the United States), Pfizer and Takeda.

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Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
Abcam	ab271142	CVCL_0030	HeLa	WT
Abcam	ab262511	CVCL_B1L8	HeLa	<i>BECN1</i> KO
ATCC	HTB-14	CVCL_0022	U-87 MG	WT
ATCC	CCL-121	CVCL_0317	HT-1080	WT
ATCC	HTB-43	CVCL_1218	FaDu	WT
ATCC	CRL-2062	CVCL_1177	DMS 53	WT
JCRB Cell Bank	JCRB0192	CVCL_3084	OCUM-1	WT
ATCC	CCL-247	CVCL_0291	HCT 116	WT
ATCC	HTB-26	CVCL_0062	MDA-MB-231	WT
ATCC	CCL-185	CVCL_0023	A549	WT

Table 2: Summary of the Beclin-1 antibodies tested in western blot and immunoprecipitation

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{L}$)	Vendors recommended applications
Abcam	ab207612**	1008184-30	AB_2692326	recombinant mono	EPR19662	rabbit	0.63	Wb, IP
Abcam	ab210498**	1007371-36	AB_2810879	recombinant mono	EPR20473	rabbit	0.48	Wb, IP
ABclonal	A21191**	3522122864	NA	recombinant mono	ARC52856	rabbit	1.00	Wb, IF
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP58595_P050	QC26094- 40647	AB_2045088	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.50	Wb
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP58873_P050	QC29849- 41486	AB_3698285	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.50	Wb
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP58874_P050	QC74235- 200313	AB_10714114	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.50	Wb
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP86768_P050	QC62832- 42977	AB_3698309	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.50	Wb
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP86769_P050	QC62833- 42977	AB_3698310	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.50	Wb
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP97266_P050	QC68462- 43264	AB_3698315	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.50	Wb
Bio-Techne (Novus Biologicals)	NBP3-32076**	H651612014	AB_3698350	recombinant mono	JE59-31	rabbit	1.00	Wb, IF
Bio-Techne (R&D Systems)	MAB5295*	CERI0122051	AB_10920932	monoclonal	669922	mouse	0.50	Wb
Cell Signaling Technology	3495**	7	AB_1903911	recombinant mono	D40C5	rabbit	0.11	Wb, IP
GeneTex	GTX133555	45385	AB_2887020	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.61	Wb
MilliporeSigma	ZRB1222**	Q3284854	AB_3698362	recombinant mono	1E22	rabbit	0.30	Wb, IF
Proteintech	11306-1-AP	00148624	AB_2259061	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.60	Wb, IP, IF
Proteintech	66665-1-Ig*	10024164	AB_2882020	monoclonal	1C10C4	mouse	1.50	Wb
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-15825*	AC4649936	AB_11153717	monoclonal	2A4	mouse	NA	Wb, IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-51201**	AC4650227B	AB_3094195	recombinant mono	9D8K9	rabbit	1.00	Wb, IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-51469**	AC4650229B	AB_3094193	recombinant mono	6W4G3	rabbit	1.20	Wb, IF

Wb=western blot; IP=immunoprecipitation; IF= immunofluorescence, **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody, NA=not available

Table 3: Summary of the Beclin-1 antibodies tested in flow cytometry

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration (µg/µL)	Vendors recommended applications
Abcam	ab207612**	1088918-12	AB_2692326	recombinant mono	EPR19662	Rabbit	0.57	Wb, IP
Abcam	ab210498**	1007371-49	AB_2810879	recombinant mono	EPR20473	Rabbit	0.48	Wb, IP
Abcam	ab252609**	1116701-2	NA	recombinant mono	EPR20473-245	Rabbit	1.05	other
Abcam	ab252668**	1116697-2	NA	recombinant mono	EPR20473-221	Rabbit	1.00	other
ABclonal	A21191**	3522122864	NA	recombinant mono	ARC52856	Rabbit	1.00	Wb, IF
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP58874_P050	QC74235-200313	AB_10714114	polyclonal	-	Rabbit	0.50	Wb
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP86768_P050	QC62832-42977	AB_3698309	polyclonal	-	Rabbit	0.50	Wb
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP97266_P050	QC68462-43264	AB_3698315	polyclonal	-	Rabbit	0.50	Wb
Cell Signaling Technology	3495**	7	AB_1903911	recombinant mono	D40C5	Rabbit	0.11	Wb, IP
GeneTex	GTX133555	45448	AB_2887020	polyclonal	-	Rabbit	0.61	Wb
Proteintech	11306-1-AP	00146927	AB_2259061	polyclonal	-	Rabbit	0.60	Wb, IP, IF
Proteintech	66665-1-Ig*	10024164	AB_2882020	monoclonal	1C10C4	Mouse	1.50	Wb
R&D Systems	MAB5295*	CERI0122051	AB_10920932	monoclonal	669922	Mouse	0.10	Wb
Sigma-Aldrich	ZRB1222**	RA1904110	AB_3698362	recombinant mono	1E22	Rabbit	0.30	Wb, IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-15825*	160520-2025	AB_11153717	monoclonal	2A4	Mouse	NA	Wb, IF, FC
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-51201**	79635494	AB_3094195	recombinant mono	9D8K9	Rabbit	1.00	Wb, IF

Wb=western blot; IP=immunoprecipitation; IF= immunofluorescence, FC= Flow Cytometry **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody, NA=not available

Table 4: Table of secondary antibodies used

Company	Secondary antibody	Catalog number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Concentration (µg/µL)	Working concentration (µg/mL)
Proteintech	HRP-Goat Anti-Rabbit Antibody (H+L)	RGAR001	AB_3073505	recombinant polyclonal	1.0	0.05
Proteintech	HRP-Goat Anti-Mouse Antibody (H+L)	RGAM001	AB_3068333	recombinant polyclonal	1.0	0.5
Cell Signaling Technology	Protein A, HRP conjugate	12291	NA	polyclonal	0.125	0.5
Proteintech	CoraLite Plus 647-Goat Anti-Rabbit Antibody (H+L)	RGAR005	AB_3073509	recombinant polyclonal	0.5	0.83
Proteintech	CoraLite Plus 647-Goat Anti-Mouse Antibody (H+L)	RGAM005	AB_3073503	recombinant polyclonal	0.5	0.83

Table 5: Illustrations to assess antibody performance in western blot, immunoprecipitation and flow cytometry

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Figure 1: Beclin-1 antibody screening by western blot

Tissue type	Cell line	RNA score (log2 TPM+1)
Cervical Adenocarcinoma	HeLa	5.7
Diffuse Glioma	U-87 MG	6.4
Fibrosarcoma	HT-1080	6.4
Head and Neck Squamous Cell Carcinoma	FaDu	6.4
Lung Neuroendocrine Tumor	DMS 53	6.3
Esophagogastric Adenocarcinoma	OCUM-1	6.2
Colorectal Adenocarcinoma	HCT 116	6.2
Invasive Breast Carcinoma	MDA-MB-231	6.1
Non-Small Cell Lung Cancer	A549	5.9

Figure 2: Differential expression of Beclin-1 detected by western blot in various cell lysates

Figure 3: Beclin-1 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Figure 4: Beclin-1 antibody screening by flow cytometry (1/2)

Figure 4: Beclin-1 antibody screening by flow cytometry (2/2)

FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1: Beclin-1 antibody screening by western blot.

Lysates of HeLa WT and *BECN1* KO were prepared, and 30µg of protein were processed for western blot with the indicated Beclin-1 antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are presented to show equal loading of WT and KO lysates and protein transfer efficiency from the acrylamide gels to the nitrocellulose membrane. Antibody dilutions were chosen according to the recommendations of the antibody supplier. Antibody dilutions used: ab207612** at 1/2000, ab210498** at 1/1000, A21191** at 1/2000, ARP58595 at 1/500, ARP58873 at 1/500, ARP58874 at 1/500, ARP86768 at 1/500, ARP86769 at 1/500, ARP97266 at 1/500, NBP3-32076** at 1/500, MAB5295* at 1/5000, 3495** at 1/1000, GTX133555 at 1/1000, ZRB1222** at 1/1000, 11306-1-AP at 1/1000, 66665-1-Ig* at 1/2000, MA5-15825* at 1/1000, MA5-51201** 1/2000, MA5-51469** at 1/8000. Predicted band size: 51.8 kDa. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.

Figure 2: Differential expression of Beclin-1 detected by western blot in various cell lysates.

Western blot was performed with anti-Beclin-1 MA5-51201** at 1/2000, and using lysates from HeLa (WT and *BECN1* KO), U-87 MG, HT-1080, FaDu, DMS 53, OCUM-1, HCT 116, MDA-MB-231 and A549. Predicted band size: 51.8 kDa. **= recombinant antibody.

Figure 3: Beclin-1 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation.

HeLa lysates were prepared, and immunoprecipitation was performed for 1 h using 1 mg of lysate and 2.0 µg of the indicated Beclin-1 antibodies pre-coupled to Dynabeads protein A or protein G. Samples were washed and processed for western blot with the Beclin-1 antibody MA5-51201** used at 1/2000. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. SM=6% starting material; UB=6% unbound fraction; IP=immunoprecipitate. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.

Figure 4: Beclin-1 antibody screening by flow cytometry.

HeLa WT and *BECN1* KO cells were labelled with a green or violet, fluorescent dye, respectively. WT and KO cells were mixed in a 1:1 ratio, fixed in 4% PFA and permeabilized in 0.1% Triton X-100. 400,000 cells were stained with the indicated Beclin-1 antibodies and corresponding Multi-rAb CoraLite® Plus 647 secondary antibodies. Antibody staining was quantified using the Attune NxT Flow Cytometer with representative images showing the staining intensity in the KO population (pink histogram, dashed line) compared to the WT cells (green histogram, solid line). Histograms with dotted lines represent secondary antibody-only controls in both WT and KO cells. Antibody dilutions used: ab207612** at 1/5750, ab210498** at 1/4830, ab252609** at 1/10570, ab252668** at 1/10050, A21191** at 1/10000, ARP58874-P050 at 1/5000, ARP86768-P050 at 1/5000, ARP97266-P050 at 1/5000, 3495** at 1/1110, GTX133555 at 1/6100, 11306-1-AP at 1/6000, 66665-1-Ig* at 1/1500, MAB5295* at 1/10000, ZRB1222** at 1/3000, MA5-15825* at 1/1000, MA5-51201** at 1/10 000. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.